

Expected Work Experience and the Gender Wage Gap:

A New Human Capital Measure

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Abstract: Work experience is a key variable in earnings function estimates and wage gap decompositions. Because data on actual work experience are rare, studies commonly use proxies, such as potential experience. But potential experience is identical for all individuals of the same age and level of education, so it ignores labor market intermittency because of child birth and child rearing—a critical omission when analyzing gender differences in earnings. This paper constructs a better proxy: expected work experience—the sum of the annual probabilities that an individual worked in the past. This measure can be generated using commonly available data on labor force participation rates by age and gender to gauge the probability of past work. Applying the measure to labor force survey data from the Philippines shows that conventional proxies underestimate the contribution of gender differences in work experience in explaining the gender wage gap.

Keywords: potential experience, gender wage gap, Philippines, women's relative earnings, wage regressions

JEL Codes: J16, J24, J31, O15, O53

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1. Introduction

Work experience is a key observable productivity characteristic in human capital earnings function estimates and wage gap decompositions. Because data on actual work experience are rare, studies commonly use potential experience to proxy for actual experience (see, for example, Appleton *et al.* 1999, Blau and Kahn 2003, and Gannon *et al.* 2007). This variable is calculated as age minus years of education minus six (assuming most children start school at age six). This proxy, however, is the same for every individual of the same age and education level, regardless of gender. Many women have some labor market intermittency because of child birth and child rearing, and potential experience does not account for this discontinuity in labor force attachment (Miller 1993). For these women, potential experience will overestimate their actual experience and underestimate the male–female gap in actual work experience. Differentials in labor force attachment can also affect the accuracy of potential experience measures for immigrants and minority men (Hum and Simpson 2004; Antecol and Bedard 2004).

Moreover, the average level of potential experience will change over time only with changes in educational attainment (which reduce average potential experience as average education levels rise) and with changes in the age structure of the workforce. Potential experience therefore neglects key gender, racial, ethnic, and generational differences in workforce attachment. The problem in obtaining accurate estimates of the determinants of earnings is compounded when the underlying dataset excludes information on participation in training programs, union membership, number and age of children, and other relevant information. Such omissions in country labor force surveys are widespread, especially in lower- and middle-income countries.

To deal with this problem, we construct a better proxy for actual work experience that relies on commonly available labor market indicators. This new approach is useful for developing country settings or historical analysis where direct measures of work experience and tenure are not available. This paper launches a new proxy for actual experience—we call this expected work experience—which is the sum of work probabilities for all years that a person has been of working age. Work probabilities could in principle be made contingent on a range of other factors, but data availability becomes a problem. Our solution is to base work probabilities on long-term historical information on labor force participation rates by age and gender. This paper is not the first to propose an improved proxy for accumulated work experience, but it is the first to use the measure of expected work experience, and it is designed specifically with data-sparse conditions in mind.

This measure can be applied to labor market studies for developing countries, such as the example of the Philippines in this paper, and to long-term historical analysis of wages and employment. We chose the Philippines as a case study because it has extremely good historical data on male and female labor force participation rates over time, the key data series used to construct our measure of expected work experience. That said, the Philippines is an unusual country in terms of the gender wage gap: it is conspicuous for having near gender earnings parity—a rarity globally, not just for its income level. The Philippines also stands out as a developing country where women have an advantage over men in terms of obtaining a formal education. Moreover, a relatively high share (approximately half) of female paid employees have college educations compared to other countries with similar levels of GDP per capita and compared to all women in the working-age population in the Philippines (Asian Development Bank 2015). Finally, gender wage gaps in the Philippines are relatively understudied. The little

available published evidence does point to gender discrimination in wages (as proxied by the residual wage gap), especially in lower quantiles of the wage distribution (Sakellariou 2004), and to a relatively larger positive response for women compared to men in the returns to improved school quality in elementary school (Yamauchi and Liu 2018). Further gender differences are found in Rodgers and Menon (2012) regarding the labor market repercussions of the 2008-09 global financial crisis, with evidence of a small increase in the residual gender wage gap in the Philippines as employers struggled to adjust costs in the wake of the crisis. All three of these earlier studies used potential experience or worker age to proxy for labor market experience, with the implication that patterns in the explained and unexplained portions of the wage gap may have differed had a better proxy been used.

2. Literature review

Labor economists have long recognized the importance of having a measure of labor market experience or on-the-job training in estimations of earnings functions (Mincer 1958; Becker 1962). Data on actual work experience are usually sourced from longitudinal datasets such as the National Longitudinal Surveys (NLS) and the Panel Study of Income Dynamics (PSID) in the United States. In the absence of direct information on work experience, economists typically use potential work experience. This measure, introduced by Mincer (1974), is obtained by subtracting years of schooling and age at the start of schooling (usually six) from the reported age. While this measure may be appropriate in some contexts, it is inadequate for individuals who have interruptions in their work experience. Hence when there is work intermittency, potential experience does not accurately represent the duration of employment. This issue is important for women because they are more likely than men to drop out of the labor force for

child birth and child rearing. These interruptions in work experience translate into reduced job tenure and less on-the-job training for women and can contribute to the gender pay gap (Mincer and Polachek 1974). Using the common measure of potential experience overestimates actual years of work experience for women and underestimates the contribution of gender differences in work experience in explaining the total gender wage gap (Regan and Oaxaca 2009). The issue of work disruptions has also taken on added importance after the 2008 financial global crisis because of the increase in long-term unemployment and anemic job recovery (Blau and Kahn 2013). For these reasons, reliable measures of actual work experience are preferable to potential experience in the analysis of earnings determinants.

Ideally, questions about retrospective labor market experience can be added to existing labor market surveys, household surveys, or surveys of population segments, especially in developing countries where no reliable information on actual work experience exists. This approach, however, may not be a priority for these countries because of the limited capacity of their statistical offices. When actual work experience is not available, a practical alternative is to estimate experience equations using an alternative dataset that contains actual experience or work history, and then predicting experience by applying the coefficients from these equations to observed characteristics from the original dataset. In other words, while labor force surveys typically do not capture actual work experience, their information can be used to approximate the probability that an individual has worked in a year, contingent on certain observable characteristics and the use of parameters estimated with another data source that has some information on work histories.

This approach was followed in Garvey and Reimers (1979), which used a dataset containing detailed information on work histories, including hours of work, to predict total

working-hour experience for individuals based on their demographic characteristics. They then used this prediction formula for work experience together with a dataset that did not have information on actual experience and found that it yielded improved earnings function estimates for women relative to the standard potential experience measure. A similar process was followed in Moulton (1986) using U.S. Social Security data to construct predicted experience and then applying that measure to earnings function estimates based on the commonly-used Current Population Survey, which has detailed demographic information but does not include actual experience.

In an extension of this strategy, Filer (1993) estimated equations that predict work experience by occupation. To reflect the expected divergence in career patterns across occupations, Filer used NLS data and estimated actual work experience for women across occupation categories. Experience equations were estimated using ordinary least squares with the number of years of work experience regressed on numerous demographic variables. This occupation-specific predicted experience variable was shown to be preferable over potential experience in estimating earnings functions using another data set that lacked actual experience. Results also suggested that using potential experience can lead to biased estimates of the effects of some characteristics such as race and schooling on women's earnings. Subsequent results for the U.S. in Regan and Oaxaca (2009) comparing predicted experience (constructed with actual experience from a separate data set) with potential experience confirmed that using potential experience biases the estimated rates of return from schooling and labor market experience, leading to underestimates of the explained portion of the gender wage gap.

These studies discussed thus far still require some sort of information on work histories or work experience to predict actual experience. This kind of data may simply not be available

for developing countries or even for long-term historical analyses of industrialized countries. The fallback option is to use potential experience. However, if women spend less time in the labor force than men due to family responsibilities, they accumulate actual work experience at a slower rate than men. Social changes that see younger women spending more time in paid employment than previous generations will cause the probability of work experience for individuals of a given age to rise over time. Using age or potential experience as a proxy for actual work experience cannot capture these important labor market dynamics. In the next section we propose an alternative measure that does not require any individual-level data on work history or experience.

3. Calculation of expected work experience

In the absence of data on actual work experience, researchers can use a prediction equation to approximate individuals' accumulated experience when modeling labor market outcomes.¹ To this end, let ρ_{it} denote the probability that person i is working during period t . In principle, observed worked characteristics at time T , Θ_{iT} , can be used to infer actual work experience. That is, expected work experience is equal to the sum of the probability that a person has worked in each period from the usual age of entering the workforce (denoted time zero) to today:

$$\Lambda_{iT} = \sum_{t=0}^T \text{Exp}[\rho_{it} \mid \Theta_{iT}]. \quad (1)$$

Proxy variables like potential experience implicitly assume all individuals accumulate work experience at the same rate over time (that is, $\rho_{it} = 1$ for all years following school completion).

¹ The discussion in this paper is limited to proxy measures for the quantity of job market experience, not its quality. An expanded view of work experience that considers quality differences would be even more information intensive, requiring data on the type of work as well as time worked.

This assumption is especially problematic when studying gender differences in labor market outcomes. The accuracy of predicted accumulated experience could conceivably be improved with more detail on employee characteristics and better estimates of how these characteristics translate into time spent working in the past. However, this information may not be readily available. In contrast, labor force participation rates by age and gender are widely available for long periods of time, making them ideal candidates for the expected probability of employment. Conditional on an individual's age today and gender, the expected work probability can be approximated by the age–gender labor force participation rates that have prevailed since the person reached working age.

As an example of this approximation, let λ_{jt}^f denote the labor force participation rate for women of age j at time t . Limiting the set of known worker characteristics to age and gender, the work experience a woman is expected to have gained in period t is $\text{Exp}[\rho_t^f \mid \text{age}_t = j] = \lambda_{jt}^f$. For a woman who is age J today and assuming her working age begins at 15, her expected work experience can be calculated from equation (1) as follows:

$$\widehat{\Lambda}_{JT}^f = \sum_{j=15}^J \lambda_{j,T-J+j}^f . \quad (2)$$

Consider the practical example of a woman in the Philippines age 23 in 2015. The labor force participation rates her cohort faced during 2007–2014 were approximately 25% each year for ages 15–19 and 53% each year for ages 22–24. As such, her expected labor force experience in 2015 is around 2.8 years by Equation (2). The procedure for men is the same, using labor force participation rates for men rather than women. Expected work experience will differ across men and women of the same age at a given point in time depending on the prevailing labor force participation rates during their working years. Similarly, comparisons of expected work

experience for the same age cohort of women at different points in time will vary as the age profiles of the labor force participation rates of women change.

Using potential experience as a proxy does not capture these differences. For a man or woman age J at any point in time t whose postschool work experience begins at age 18 (roughly a high school graduate), the value of potential experience would be the difference between their age and when they started to work. In the hypothetical case above, the woman would have $23-18=5$ years of potential experience. Average gender differences in potential experience would only arise from gender differences in age composition of the workforce and gender differences in average education rates. In contrast, average expected work experience captures these differences as well as other forms of labor market intermittency, such as withdrawal from the labor market related to marriage, child rearing, or military service. If the same gender-age cohorts are compared at different points in time, potential experience will only capture the negative impact that increased years of schooling has on measured work experience. Expected work experience captures this as well, since increased years of schooling would be reflected in the lower labor force participation rates of the young. However, it also captures the effect of other social changes that influence the labor force attachment of men and women, such as smaller family size or improved access to child care.

How well does expected work experience track actual work experience? We test the proxy measure against reported cumulative work experience collected in the NLSY79 (Bureau of Labor Statistics 2016). The survey has tracked the same group of individuals since 1979, including retrospective questions covering 1978. The 1979 sample comprised 12,686 individuals—split nearly evenly between men and women—born from 1957 to 1964. The midyear ages of the initial sample ranged from 14 to 22 years. The respondents were surveyed

annually from 1979 to 1994 and once every two years thereafter for a total of 26 rounds as of the most recent survey in 2014. In this survey, respondents' midyear ages ranged from 49 to 52 years. Over time, some respondents were permanently dropped from further interviews while others were not interviewed for other reasons, such that complete work histories can be constructed for only 7,071 respondents from the original sample.² Women make up 52% of the sample with complete work histories.

We calculate actual work in a year as total weeks spent in civilian employment in a year. Cumulative work experience is calculated beginning at age 21 since information for work at younger ages is not available for all NLSY79 respondents. Work histories by age can be calculated for all 7,071 respondents only up to and including age 49. For consistency, expected work experience is also calculated assuming that work experience begins from age 21. Labor force participation rates by gender and age groups (20–24, 25–35, 36–45, 46–55) for 1978–2014 are used to calculate expected work experience. We also calculate potential experience as a reference, assuming postschool work experience begins at age 21 in order to maintain consistency with the measure of actual cumulative work experience.

Fig. 1 shows the distribution of actual work experience in the NLSY79 sample for every age from 21 to 49 using box plots, and it compares the results with potential experience and our measure of expected work experience for each year of age. For each year, the median of actual

² NLSY79 is composed of three independent probability samples: (i) a sample chosen to be nationally representative of the young, noninstitutional civilian population (6,111 respondents in the first survey round), (ii) a supplemental sample designed to oversample the economically disadvantaged (5,295 respondents), and (iii) a sample representative of those serving in the military (1,280 respondents). After the 1984 survey round, 1,079 members of the military sample were dropped. After the 1990 survey round, 1,643 nonblack and non-Hispanic members of the economically disadvantaged supplemental sample were dropped. In the 2014 survey round, 790 respondents were reported deceased, 515 could not be located, 1,121 refused to be interviewed, and 467 were not interviewed for other reasons.

work experience is measured by the horizontal line inside the box, and the upper and lower ends of each box represent the upper and lower quartiles of actual work experience for that age. Expected experience and potential experience are represented by the line graphs; for each year of age and gender, there is no variation in expected experience or potential experience. The relationship between age and potential experience is linear by construction. Also by construction, potential experience is the upper bound of the actual experience range, with potential work experience equal to age minus 20 for every year of age. As shown by the length of the boxes in the box plots, the range of actual work experience in the NLSY79 is quite broad, nearly spanning the possible range of outcomes of no work experience to potential experience regardless of gender or age. The expected work experience proxy performs well, closely tracking the median value of actual work experience for both men and women.³ The relationship is closer for men, with expected work experience overstating actual work experience at the median by less than half a year for men 49 years of age. For women, the proxy somewhat understates actual experience by about 1 year at age 49. Although the expected work proxy overestimates the NLSY79 gender experience gap by 1.6 years at age 49, it does capture the fact that the experience gap tends to widen with age, unlike the potential experience gap.

³ We also calculated cumulative work experience for the full sample of 12,686 NLSY79 respondents by setting unreported work experience at zero. As expected, the resulting work experience distributions had lower values at the 25th, 50th, and 75th percentiles for all age groups. In this case, expected work experience tended to track the 75th percentile of the distributions for men and closer to the 60th percentile for women.

Fig. 1. Comparison of work history with estimated and potential work experience in the National Longitudinal Survey of Youth 1979. The box plot shows the distribution of actual work experience in the NLSY79 sample by age. For each year of age, vertical lines show the whole range of actual work experience with the boxes on each line indicating the 25th to 75th percentile and the median marked with bold line. Expected experience and potential experience are represented by the line graphs; for each year of age and gender, there is no variation in expected experience or potential experience.

Source: Authors' calculations.

4. Application: expected work experience in the Philippines

To illustrate the usefulness of this proxy, the technique is applied to labor force data from the Philippines. Data availability—and even its limitations—make the country an ideal test case for the feasibility of the methodology. While the Philippines does not have panel data documenting actual work experience, it does have relatively long time-series data on labor force participation by age and sex from a variety of sources. The need to deal with data gaps and shifting definitions of labor force participation illustrates the types of problems that are faced in constructing expected work experience in a typical developing country setting.

4.1. *Expected work experience results*

This analysis uses labor force participation rates for age–gender groups to proxy for work probabilities. These rates for the Philippines are constructed from census data, published labor force statistics, and household survey data. We construct rates for six consistent gender-disaggregated age groups: 15–19, 20–24, 25–34, 35–44, 45–54, and 55–64. The process is not without its challenges. Notably, historical data are missing in some cases, largely because expected work experience for older workers requires long time series. To calculate the expected experience for the oldest age group in 2001, the earliest year for which wage data are available, we need labor force participation rates for the youngest age group going back to 1952. Another challenge is comparability in definitions of work over time and across the census data and household survey data.⁴

⁴ The labor force participation rate is calculated as those either employed or unemployed as a percent of the working-age, noninstitutional population. For household survey data in the Philippines, the definition of unemployed was changed, leading to slightly lower levels of labor force participation for both men and women. Although the change was adopted in 2005, the Philippine Statistical Authority includes information in the Labor Force Survey microdata from 1991 onward to construct labor force status according to both the new and old definitions. In contrast, the Philippines *1975 Integrated Census of the Population and Its Economic Activities* queried respondents about “gainful” and “non-gainful” occupations. This approach blurs the distinction between

Data from all sources were used to generate a complete annual series of labor force participation by age and gender. Logit transformations⁵ of age–gender labor force participation rates were regressed on a linear time trend plus dummy variables for the changes in the definition of work in the census and household surveys and a dummy for the years of the Asian financial crisis and its immediate aftermath (1997–2000). The logit transformation was used to ensure that extrapolated fitted values range between 0% and 100%. The constructed series implicitly adopt the latest definition of labor force participation by setting the values of the census and old definition dummies to zero when generating fitted values.

The constructed series are plotted with the published data from the various sources in Fig. 2. The shapes of the markers represent the three sources of data and changing definitions of labor force participation, with the squares indicating data points from the census, hollow circles indicating calculations based with all three data sources using an earlier definition of labor force participation, and triangles indicating calculations using the updated definition. The straight lines represent the line of best fit for women (lower) and men (higher). The figure shows the Philippines has seen increasing the labor force participation rates of women across most age groups, but not men. This finding is similar for many other developing countries (Mammen and Paxson 2000). Only women ages 15–19 have seen declining participation rates, reflecting their increasing likelihood of staying in school longer. Unlike the increase in labor force participation for women in their prime working age, labor force participation rates for men have stayed fairly constant for the prime working-age cohorts. They have fallen for very young and very mature

those who are unemployed, working without pay, or out of the work force compared to the more specific definition used by the Labor Force Survey.

⁵ The logit transformation of the labor force participation rate λ is defined as $\text{logit}(\lambda) = \ln(\lambda) - \ln(1-\lambda)$.

men, and risen slightly for men in their early 20s. Because the rates are rising for women and staying fairly constant for men, women's accumulated work experience at a given age will be

Fig. 2. Estimated labor force participation rates by age and sex in the Philippines, 1951–2015. The shapes of the markers represent the three sources of data and changing definitions of labor force participation, with the squares indicating data points from the census, hollow circles indicating calculations based on all three data sources using an earlier definition of labor force participation, and triangles indicating calculations using the updated definition. The straight lines represent the line of best fit for females (solid) and males (dashed).
Source: Authors' calculations.

higher for more recent cohorts compared to cohorts of the same age in the more distant past. Hence, the gender gap in accumulated experience is narrowing over time.

These changes in actual work experience are unlikely to be captured in typical proxy variables, such as age or potential work experience. This argument is illustrated in Fig. 3 using historical data on labor force participation in the Philippines for 2 worker cohorts: those age 20 beginning in 1970 and those age 20 beginning in 1995. Expected work experience is calculated based on Equation (2) assuming working age begins at 15 for both cohorts. To abstract from the effects of gender differences in education rates and their changes over time, as well as to be comparable with the expected work experience series, potential experience is calculated assuming all individuals begin accumulating work experience from age 15. The figure shows that expected work experience of women in the Philippines has increased over time across age cohorts, while expected experience has stayed virtually the same for men. These patterns in expected work experience are consistent with the finding that women's labor force participation has risen over time while it has stayed the same for men overall.

4.2. Wage decomposition methodology

The strength of the expected work experience proxy is best illustrated in a practical example: a decomposition of gender wage differentials. This analysis uses micro-level data from the National Statistics Office's quarterly Labor Force Survey. The data constitute a nationally representative sample and are used by the government to construct official labor market

Fig. 3. Years of expected work experience versus potential experience in the Philippines. Expected experience is calculated using Equation (2) in the paper, with experience accumulating from age 15. Potential experience is calculated as age minus 16, which assumes post-school work experience begins from age 15. The figure shows expected experience for two cohorts of female male workers: those who were age 20 in 1970 and those who were age 20 in 1995. Source: Authors' calculations.

indicators. For the empirical work, we pooled repeated cross sections of the quarterly releases of the Labor Force Surveys from 2001 to 2015. The full sample retains all civilians ages 15 to 65 with observed values for the key regressors. The wage sample draws from the employment sample and keeps all individuals with positive reported daily basic wages, including wage

workers and salaried employees but excluding live-in domestic workers.⁶ Nominal daily wage rates are deflated using the value of the National Statistics Office's monthly consumer price index corresponding to the reference period of the survey to compute real wages.

Because the wage sample excludes people out of the labor force and the self-employed, who do not report a daily basic wage, it is considerably smaller than the overall sample. To the extent that women are more likely than men to select out of paid employment, our wage estimates could be subject to sample selection bias in which women's earnings are overstated and the gender earnings gap is understated. Typically, individuals from the lower end of the earnings distribution are more likely to select out of paid employment than are those from the upper tail. This result is common for women, since they have lower labor force participation rates than men. Although the magnitude of this selection effect is often larger for women, the selection effect declines over time as labor force participation rates for women increase.⁷

The gender wage gap can be decomposed into an explained and an unexplained portion. Using a fairly standard application of the Oaxaca-Blinder procedure, we decompose the gender wage gap in each year into a portion explained by average group differences in productivity characteristics and a residual portion that is commonly attributed to discrimination (Oaxaca 1973; Blinder 1973). The explained gap is the portion of the gap attributed to gender differences in measured productivity characteristics; the residual gap is the portion attributed to gender

⁶ The daily basic wage is the pay for normal work time before deductions for taxes, social security, and other withholdings. The concept excludes nonregular cash payments such as allowances, commissions, and overtime; it also excludes in-kind benefits and compensation.

⁷ A common procedure to deal with selection bias is to use a two-step Heckman correction procedure that first estimates the likelihood of inclusion in the wage sample and calculates what is known as an inverse Mills' ratio, and then includes this ratio as an explanatory variable in the wage estimations. The effectiveness of this procedure hinges on the inclusion of additional variables that are plausible predictors of paid employment but are not associated with wages. However, findings for other developing economies suggests that the selection parameter accounts for a negligible portion of the gender wage gap (Zveglic et al. 1997). Our data set for the Philippines did not contain such variables so we did not perform the correction procedure.

differences in market returns to those characteristics. To perform the decomposition, a human capital earnings function is estimated for male employees in each year in each economy, and the coefficients from the male regression are used to calculate predicted log wages for male and female workers. An argument for using male coefficients—the approach followed by most studies of this type in the literature (Oaxaca and Ranson 1994)—is that they more accurately reflect competitive returns to measured characteristics than female coefficients. Residual log wages are simply the difference between actual log wages and predicted log wages.

The determinants of real wages for men are expressed as follows:

$$W_i = a + \beta_1 T_i + \beta_2 Edu_i + \beta_3 Exp_i + \beta_4 Ind/Occ_i + \beta_5 X_i + \vartheta_i , \quad (3)$$

where i denotes an employee. The dependent variable W_i represents the real value of wages received, and the remaining variables are individual and household characteristics that influence people's wages. These characteristics include time inputs, such as hours per day or days per week, (T_i); a set of dummy variables for educational attainment (Edu_i); and a measure of experience and experience squared (Exp_i). The matrix Ind/Occ_i represents controls for industries and occupations where industries include agriculture (hunting, forestry, and fishing, among other sectors); mining and quarrying; manufacturing; electricity, gas and water; construction; wholesale and retail trade; restaurants and hotels; communications; financial and real estate services; and community, social, and personal services. Occupational categories include professional, technical, and related workers; administrative, executive, and managerial workers; clerical and related workers; sales and service workers; farmers, fishermen, hunters, and loggers; production and related workers; and transport equipment operators and laborers. Most of these variables are fairly standard control variables in wage regressions across countries.

The matrix X_i includes geographic indicators, such as urban residence and state or province of residence, and other demographic variables. The geographical variables control for local labor market conditions that may affect people's employment and earnings. The term ϑ_i is an individual-specific idiosyncratic error term. All regressions are weighted using sample weights provided in the data sources.

Table 1 provides sample means of the variables used in the analysis of labor market trends and in the wage gap decomposition analysis. The sample statistics are demarcated by gender, the first year and the last year of the data, and by the sample used (wage and full sample). The table shows that real weekly pay has fallen over time in the Philippines. The high incidence of part time work among wage earners for both women and men is also noteworthy. Women do have an advantage over men in formal education. For industries, 8% of women and 18% of men in the Philippines work in agriculture. But once we look at all individuals of working age, including unpaid family workers, the dominance of the rural sector becomes more apparent. The importance of manufacturing as a sector of employment declines over time for men and women, being replaced instead by mining, utilities, and construction. Among the other variables, paid workers live predominantly in urban areas. About two-thirds of men and women in the samples are married, and the number of preschool children (0–5 years) has declined in households.

4.3. *Wage decomposition results*

The empirical analysis for trends in gender pay gaps begins by examining changes in the mean unadjusted female-to-male earnings ratio. Because changes in this ratio can arise from changes in gender differences in observed characteristics, such as education and experience, we also calculate adjusted earnings ratios. These ratios are constructed as the ratio of female to male

Table 1

Wage function estimation variable definitions and averages in the Philippines
(%, unless otherwise indicated)

Variable	Women				Men			
	2001		2015		2001		2015	
	Wage sample	Full sample						
Real basic daily pay (₱, 2006 prices)	228.6		210.8		221.1		214.3	
Normal daily hours worked (hours)	7.7		7.8		8.0		7.9	
Part time work	23.9		20.9		23.0		21.0	
Education								
No formal education	0.8	2.3	0.4	1.3	0.9	2.0	0.6	1.5
Primary incomplete	8.2	11.7	5.5	7.7	13.7	15.4	11.8	12.8
Primary graduate	12.5	17.1	7.8	10.4	16.6	16.2	11.8	12.0
High school incomplete	8.8	17.1	7.8	15.1	14.4	18.5	13.2	16.5
High school graduate	21.5	22.8	32.0	34.4	26.9	23.1	36.8	32.8
College incomplete	13.2	15.6	9.4	14.2	14.1	15.6	9.4	12.4
College graduate	35.1	13.4	37.2	17.0	13.3	9.3	16.4	12.2
Experience (years)								
Age	34.8	34.8	34.4	34.0	34.8	33.9	34.4	33.9
Years of schooling	10.3	8.8	10.8	9.6	8.8	8.4	9.2	8.9
Potential experience	18.2	19.5	17.4	18.2	19.5	18.9	18.8	18.5
Estimated work experience	8.9	9.0	9.2	9.1	15.6	15.1	15.1	14.9
Industry								
Agriculture, forestry, and fishing	10.8		7.8		21.4		18.3	
Manufacturing	18.0		13.4		14.4		12.1	
Mining, utilities, and construction	1.2		1.3		18.9		23.2	
Wholesale and retail trade	13.4		15.2		9.6		12.4	
Transport, storage, and communications	1.6		1.7		11.8		6.2	
Business services	5.9		10.4		4.2		8.6	
Personal services	49.2		50.3		19.6		19.2	

Table 1 (continued)

Variable	Women				Men			
	2001		2015		2001		2015	
	Wage sample	Full sample						
Occupation								
Executives and managers	5.3		4.0		5.0		3.4	
Science professionals and technicians	5.7		6.1		3.3		4.3	
Other professionals and technicians	18.4		16.2		4.4		4.3	
Clerical workers	15.0		18.9		4.4		6.9	
Service and sales workers	30.3		36.2		17.0		21.7	
Agriculture, forestry, and fishing workers	10.6		7.7		20.4		17.9	
Light production workers	10.2		6.4		14.8		11.9	
Heavy production workers	4.6		4.4		30.6		29.7	
Location								
Northern Luzon	9.4	10.8	10.1	10.8	9.4	11.0	10.2	11.1
Metro Luzon	28.7	24.2	30.6	26.3	28.4	24.3	27.9	26.0
National Capital Region	19.2	15.8	17.3	13.1	17.6	14.2	16.0	12.3
Central Philippines	25.4	27.6	25.8	27.5	26.1	28.3	26.6	28.2
Mindanao	17.3	21.6	16.3	22.2	18.5	22.2	19.3	22.4
Urban area	60.7	52.5	61.4	51.5	57.0	49.9	55.8	49.4
Married	52.1	57.8	52.4	57.2	62.9	54.4	59.8	52.9
Preschool age children (number)	0.6	0.7	0.5	0.6	0.7	0.6	0.6	0.6
Number of observations	49,308	244,702	56,844	258,117	85,642	245,224	93,651	265,260

Notes: Weighted averages from pooled quarterly survey data. Consumer price index (2006 = 100) used to deflate nominal basic daily pay.

Sources: Philippine Statistics Authority, Labor Force Survey 2001, 2015; authors' calculations.

residual wages, where residual wages are the portion of wages that cannot be explained by observed productivity characteristics.

The Philippines is an unusual case compared with many other economies because it has near gender wage parity over time, with women earning relatively more than men on average in the early 2000s and slightly less than men thereafter. This pattern is illustrated in Fig. 4, which reports unadjusted and adjusted female/male earnings ratios in the Philippines from 2001 to 2015. Unadjusted earnings ratios simply compare mean reported earnings, while adjusted earnings ratios account for gender differences in observed productivity characteristics. To compute the latter, we evaluate equation (3) at the own-group means for the independent variables. We performed this estimation alternatively using potential experience and expected work experience. As shown in the figure, the unadjusted earnings ratio remained close to parity over the sample period. The main explanation for this is that women cluster in higher-paying occupations and industries than men. Women also have a relative advantage over men in educational attainment. Once all productivity characteristics are considered, including potential experience as the proxy for work experience, the adjusted female-to-male earnings ratio is considerably lower, hovering slightly above 80% in the early 2000s and slightly below or at this level for the remainder of the period. Using expected experience as the proxy for actual experience raises the adjusted female-to-male earnings ratio several percentage points each year, which makes intuitive sense since the unexplained portion of the gender earnings differential is now smaller.

One potential answer to the differences in gender earnings ratios over time comes with gender gaps in education. In the Philippines, paid employees are more educated than the overall working-age population: half of all female employees have a college education compared with less than a third of all women of working age. The Philippines still has a fairly large agricultural sector with unpaid family farm workers, which brings down the average educational attainment of the working-age population. Fig. 5 shows that in every year from 2001 to 2015, women paid

Fig. 4. Unadjusted and adjusted earnings ratios in the Philippines, 2001–2015. Unadjusted earnings ratios simply compare mean reported earnings, while adjusted earnings ratios account for gender differences in observed productivity characteristics. To compute the latter, we evaluate equation (3) at the own-group means for the independent variables. Source: Authors’ calculations.

Fig. 5. Years of schooling by gender for working-age individuals and for all paid employees in the Philippines, 2001–2015. The series for women and men of working age include unpaid workers in the agricultural sector, a relatively large segment of the population in the Philippines. Source: Authors’ calculations.

employees had roughly two more years of education compared to all women of working age, and also compared to men paid employees. On average, men of all working age had the least schooling. Educational attainment has improved substantially over time for men and women.

Gender differences in occupation and industry distributions are another source of gender disparity in earnings. Globally, women are often clustered in lower-paying jobs, while men are clustered in higher-paying positions. This source of gender disparity is explored in Table 2, which shows employment shares for women and men across major industry and occupation categories in the Philippines ranked according to average total basic pay. Unlike the common

pattern in other countries, men in the Philippines tend to be employed in lower-paying industries and occupations, while women are employed in higher-paying industry and occupation categories. For example, half of all paid female employees work in personal services, the county's third highest paying industry, compared with just 20% of men. In contrast, 20% of paid male employees work in agriculture, the lowest-paying industry, compared to just 10% of women.

Changes in gender earnings ratios may be because of changes in the productivity characteristics of women and men, as well as changes in the returns to these characteristics. Table 3 shows the results from the Oaxaca-Blinder decomposition. The first panel shows results when potential experience is included as an explanatory variable; the second panel shows the decomposition results using expected work experience to proxy for actual experience. The difference between the two panels is striking. When potential experience is used to proxy for actual experience, the gender gap in experience accounts for only 1.7 log points of the gap. But when experience is measured by expected work experience, the gender gap in experience is considerably larger, at 4.5 log points. The table shows near gender parity in wages because of the concentration of women in high-paying jobs. This concentration may be mostly due to the relatively higher levels of education of women compared with men. The explained gap actually accounts for a negative proportion of the overall earnings gaps, indicating that the proportion due to gender differences in returns to characteristics and to other unexplained factors exceeds the total wage gap. Hence, women would be paid more than men if they were paid male returns for education, experience, and their occupations and industries.

Table 2

Average industry and occupation compensation and gender employment shares in the Philippines, 2001–2015

Industry/Occupation	Mean basic pay (₱)	Women		Men	
		Employment shares (%)	Cumulative shares (%)	Employment shares (%)	Cumulative shares (%)
Industry					
Business services	332	7.6	7.6	6.7	6.7
Transport, storage, and communications	246	1.9	9.6	7.9	14.7
Personal services	239	49.9	59.4	19.4	34.1
Mining, utilities, and construction	231	1.0	60.5	20.2	54.3
Manufacturing	223	15.7	76.2	13.5	67.8
Wholesale and retail trade	189	14.5	90.7	11.4	79.2
Agriculture, forestry, and fishing	118	9.3	100.0	20.8	100.0
Occupation					
Executives and managers	486	4.3	4.3	3.9	3.9
Other professionals and technicians	446	17.2	21.6	4.4	8.3
Science professionals and technicians	407	5.6	27.1	3.7	11.9
Clerical workers	286	16.9	44.1	5.7	17.7
Heavy production workers	221	4.5	48.6	28.3	46.0
Light production workers	193	8.3	56.8	13.3	59.2
Service and sales workers	157	34.0	90.9	20.6	79.9
Agriculture, forestry, and fishing workers	116	9.1	100.0	20.1	100.0

Note: Industry and occupation groups listed in descending order of mean basic pay.

Source: Philippine Statistics Authority Labor Force Survey 2001–2015; authors' calculations.

Table 3

Oaxaca decomposition of gender earning differentials in the Philippines, 2001–2015 (male–female difference in log earnings times 100)

Years	Total gap	Gap Explained by Differences in Observables					Total explained	Residual gap
		Time	Education	Experience	Industry and occupation	Other		
Potential experience								
2001–2007	0.2	0.3	–12.4	1.8	–6.7	–0.2	–17.1	17.3
2008–2015	2.1	0.2	–13.3	1.6	–4.6	–0.6	–16.6	18.8
All years	1.2	0.3	–12.9	1.7	–5.5	–0.4	–16.9	18.1
Expected work experience								
2001–2007	0.2	0.4	–11.3	4.8	–6.7	0.0	–12.9	13.1
2008–2015	2.1	0.2	–12.2	4.2	–4.6	–0.6	–12.9	15.0
All years	1.2	0.3	–11.8	4.5	–5.6	–0.3	–12.9	14.1

Source: Authors' calculations.

5. Conclusion

This paper launched a simple methodology for improving measures of labor market experience when the actual accumulation of experience is unknown. Using readily available information on labor force participation rates by age and gender can provide greater insights into the drivers behind gender wage differences and their evolution over time, as illustrated using data from the Philippines. Like many other developing countries, the labor force participation rates for women in the Philippines have been rising while they have not changed much for men. So, for more recent cohorts, the accumulated work experience of women at a given age will be higher relative to the same age cohorts in the more distant past. This means the gender gap in accumulated experience is narrowing over time. These changes in actual work experience are not, however, captured in traditional proxy variables, such as potential experience. More troubling, the gap between potential experience and expected experience is considerably larger for women than men. Moreover, women's expected experience has risen over time across age cohorts while it has remained virtually unchanged for men. These patterns imply that using potential experience to proxy for actual experience has become increasingly problematic.

The expected experience variable can be a useful tool in empirical studies of labor markets in developing countries that lack extensive data on work histories and job tenure. Besides wage gap decompositions, other possible applications include studies of how women's human capital accumulation is related to macro-level aggregates such as technological change, remittances, and economic growth (e.g. Klasen and Lamanna 2009; Cooray *et al.* 2014, 2016; Mallick *et al.* 2017). That said, even the expected work experience has limitations as a proxy for actual work experience, particularly in a developing country context. Compared to more industrialized countries, developing countries have more fragmented labor markets with higher

incidences of multiple job holdings, seasonal work, underemployment, unpaid family work, and self-employment. To the extent that this labor market fragmentation affects women more than men, the expected experience proxy may not fully capture gender differences in years of full-time job tenure in paid employment. Additional variables to measure these particular issues would need to be added to decomposition procedures to try to identify more clearly the sources of the gender wage gap.

With this caveat in mind, our results for the Philippines show that when potential experience is used to proxy for actual work experience, the contribution of gender differences in work experience is considerably smaller than when expected work experience is used. Hence, using expected work experience as a proxy for actual work history results in a smaller residual gender wage gap. This outcome can be used to help to pinpoint policy recommendations in the Philippines and in other developing countries for improving the labor market status of women. Policies that promote women's attachment to the labor force should help to reduce gender differentials in work experience. One such policy is paid parental leave, which often has positive employment effects for women except for some cases of long leave benefits (Zveglich and Rodgers 2003). In February 2019 the president of the Philippines signed into law an expanded maternity leave policy which lengthened the duration of paid maternity leave from 60 days to 105 days and also allowed fathers to take up to 14 days of paid paternity leave.⁸ This more generous leave policy may help to narrow the gender wage gap not only by incentivizing women to remain employed, but also because it would encourage more men to take leave. The fact that childrearing is still considered women's work also results in employers "maternal profiling" all

⁸ The enactment of this new law was covered in several news sources including <https://www.rappler.com/nation/224112-fathers-can-have-14-days-paid-leave-under-new-law>.

women – regardless if they have children – and assuming they have less workplace commitment than men. Increasing access to paid paternity leave can help dismantle archaic social expectations that women serve as primary caregivers and reduce disparities between working mothers and fathers in terms of wages, labor force attachment, and caregiving responsibilities.

Policies that provide more opportunities for on-the-job training and workforce development can also help to promote women’s attachment to the labor force. In particular, outreach and education in accounting and management practices would serve as useful mechanisms for strengthening the productivity of women-owned small businesses and for increasing their ability to generate employment. Public and non-governmental institutions can play key roles by providing subsidized loans that facilitate the purchase of new profit-enhancing technologies, and by offering assistance for the marketing and sale of products created by women-run businesses. A good model is the Women Workers Employment and Entrepreneurship Development (WEED) program in the Philippines, which provides entrepreneurship training, skills development, and credit assistance to underemployed and home-based women workers, as well as women in the informal sector (Manasan 2009). Programs such as WEED can facilitate movement from low-paid work to work that is more remunerative and also help to increase women’s accumulation of human capital.

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Appendix

Table A1
Wage decomposition data and variable definitions.

Item	Description
Data source	Labor Force Survey <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Source: Philippine Statistics Authority • Pooled quarterly surveys with reference months January, April, July, October • Time span 2001–2015 (1991–2015 for labor force statistics other than wage) • Full sample includes civilians ages 15–65 with no missing information on observable characteristics • Wage function estimation subsample includes only paid workers with reported daily basic wage, but excludes live-in domestic helpers
Dependent variable	Log real daily basic wage <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Logarithm of the daily basic wage deflated using the monthly consumer price index (base year = 2006)
Time variables	Log daily hours worked <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Logarithm of normal daily hours worked in the reference week Part time work dummy <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Equal to one if respondent worked less than 40 hours in the reference week
Education variables	Education dummies [associated years of schooling in square brackets] <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • One if no formal education (omitted) [0] • One if elementary education incomplete [3] • One if elementary education complete [6] • One if high school education incomplete [8] • One if high school graduate [10] • One if college education incomplete [12] • One if college graduate [14]
Experience variables	Potential experience <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The lesser of age minus years of schooling minus 6 or age minus 12 (negative values set to zero) Potential experience squared
Industry variables	Industry dummies <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • One if agriculture, forestry, and fishing (omitted) • One if manufacturing • One if mining, utilities, and construction • One if trade • One if transport, storage, and communications • One if business services • One if social services

Item	Description
Occupation variables	Occupation dummies <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • One if legislators, senior officials, and managers • One if science, engineering, and health professionals, and associate professionals • One if other professionals and associate professionals • One if clerical workers • One if service and sales workers • One if agriculture, forestry, and fishing workers • One if light industry production workers • One if heavy industry production workers (omitted)
Other variables	Marital status dummy <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • One if married Number of preschool-age children <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The number of children ages 0 to 5 in the household Location dummies <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • One if Northern Luzon (omitted) • One if Metro Luzon • One if National Capital Region • One if Central Philippines • One if Mindanao Urban dummy <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • One if in an urban area as defined by the statistical authority Survey month dummies <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • One if January (omitted) • One if April • One if July • One if October